

Relationship of Workplace Spirituality with Positive Job Attitude (Job Satisfaction, Job Involvement and Organizational Commitment): A study of Public Sector University

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Abstract:

In a knowledge economy, people are facing increased competition hence developing more greed due to lack of love and kindness. Most of the organization now set their spiritual standards to ensure more love and kindness towards one's role and colleagues. Organizations and people should ensure workplace spirituality. This study is conducted to explore and determine the relationship between workplace spirituality, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job involvement. Our target population was employees (lecturer level) of public sector Universities of Punjab. A sample of 150 employees was selected by systematic sampling in which 101 were responded at rate of 67 %. A research questionnaire was developed for data collection and data analysis was based on descriptive and inferential statistics. As from previous studies and on basis of our hypothesis testing and data collection, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between workplace spirituality, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job involvement.

Keywords: workplace spirituality, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, job involvement, lecturer, public sector Universities.

1. Introduction

Modern world is constantly evolving at an accelerated speed in context of social, economic and environmental issues. Social, environmental and economic problems are also increasing due to increased human greed and due to lack of love and kindness. These large scale problems arising by this rapid globalization triggered in a new kind of research for peace, harmony and kindness which is a search towards spirituality. (Cacioppe, 2000) This research recognized that people in workplace work not only with hands and physical effort but they also work with heart and spirit (Ashmos, 2000) In this 21st century when the world market has been globalised, organizations are facing more complexities, intense competition and rapid structural changes which draw out the introduction of spirituality within the work environment so as to enable human hearts, morale and souls to cultivate and flush so that employees and employers will become inventive, healthy, creative, concerned, kind hearted and productive in all events to the sustenance of the workplace. (Ajala, 2013) Workplace spirituality Research is yet at its early stage and many of its aspects a yet to be investigated (Ashmos, D, & Duchon, D. (2000); B.S. Pawar, (2009); Giacalone & Jurkiewicz, (2003); Duchon & Plowman (2005); Fry, (2003))

Research on Positive work attitude and workplace spirituality identifies that spirituality at workplace affect three basic elements of positive work attitude i.e. Job Satisfaction, Job Involvement and Organizational Commitment (B.S. Pawar, 2009). Research on Job Involvement (Brown, 1996) and organizational commitment (Mathieu, 1990) indicates both situational and individual variables as antecedents of these work attitudes. Arvey (1989) identifies that both situational and individual variables are associated with job satisfaction.

Parker J. Palmer began the movement on spirituality in academia. His *The Courage to Teach* and conferences by the same title build on one idea: 'Good teaching cannot be reduced to technique [but] comes from the identity and integrity of the teacher. (Palmer, 1998) Spirituality is even more important at workplace for those who are responsible for other's learning as well. So it is important for all organizations especially educational institutes to build and support such environment which support workplace spirituality for better and more civilized learning of students by well satisfied, involved and committed teaching staff. This study is focused on University of Gujrat.

University of Gujrat is HEC recognized, one of the leading universities of Pakistan having many sub campuses. The main campus of UOG is located about 12 kilometers from the city of Gujrat in a pollution free scenic environment. It is spread over 1,000 canals. The mission of UOG is to equip the youth in the areas of economy, social policy and research, so as to enable them to compete at the international level; achieve excellence in research and teaching in all disciplines; and develop a world class centre of excellence in the industrial triangle of Gujranwala, Gujrat and Sialkot to help the industry and society at large through research-based initiatives. This study will explore workplace spirituality at University of Gujrat and its impact at job satisfaction, job involvement and organizational commitment of its employees.

1.1. Significance of Study

The main purpose of this study is to explore workplace spirituality and create awareness about workplace spirituality as well as its importance, in work setting, in both employee and employer especially associated with University of Gujrat. Workplace spirituality Research is yet at its early stage and many of its aspects a yet to be investigated so this study will add up in existing knowledge base about workplace spirituality and will help employer using workplace spirituality to get more positive work attitude of employers at work. This study will adds up to existing body of knowledge by investigating workplace spirituality and its impact on three dimensions or indicators of positive work attitude which are job satisfaction, job involvement and organizational commitment.

1.2.Objectives of the Study

Main Objective

Main objective of this study is to determine the extent to which workplace spirituality influence the level of job satisfaction, job involvement and organizational commitment of employees at University of Gujrat.

Sub Objectives

1. Determine to what extent workplace spirituality is practiced at University of Gujrat.
2. To measure the extent to which workplace spirituality leads to job satisfaction.
3. To measure the extent to which workplace spirituality leads to job involvement.
4. To measure the extent to which workplace spirituality leads to organizational commitment.

1.3. Problem Statement

Despite of widely known importance of spirituality in our lives, there is some limited consensus on the definition of spirituality and especially its importance for both employees and organization. This topic is gaining very much importance in modern life due to accelerated globalization but still there are limited studies conducted on this specific aspect of spirituality. (Ashmos, D, & Duchon, D. (2000); B.S. Pawar, (2009); Giacalone & Jurkiewicz, (2003); Duchon & Plowman (2005); Fry, (2003)). Spirituality in work setting can impact an employer's attitude towards his job and organization. There is limited knowledge existing on how spirituality at work can affect job satisfaction, job involvement and organizational commitment. Our study will be beneficial to understand the importance of workplace spirituality as well as its generated outcomes in form of job satisfaction, job involvement and organizational commitment.

2. Literature Review

2.1.Workplace Spirituality

According to Howard (2002), due to the fact that spirituality is intensely personal, though highly inclusive and widespread, it is hard to define it. Range of phenomenon associated with it includes the following: it is in the place of our hearts, inside and personal, the pursuit of trans-personal and trans-temporal truth, eternal human desire to be connected to something larger than their own ego, is everything, unification with any and everything (Hicks, 2003). Though it is highly personal, it also resides and is present in a group, an institution or in a religion which has been formed and developed

around the experiences of one or more individuals (Fry, 2003)

Anderson, P. (2000) argue that spirit of a person is a fundamental principal or animating power conventionally is thought to be the intangible, life affirming power in his self and all other human beings. According to Fairholm (1997) a person's spirit is a state of cherished affiliation with the inner self of superior values and ethics as well as acknowledgment of the truth of the inner personality of people.

Mitroff, EA Denton (1999) states that there is an accelerating and promising spirituality call in the workplace. Diverse companies such as BioGenenex, Taco Bell, Aetna International, Pizza Hut, Touche, Big Six accounting's Deloitte and Law firms such e.g. Hays & Haroller, Scholer, Fierman and New York's Kaye are extolling lessons which are often doled out in mosques, temples and churches.

Giachalone and Jurkiewicz (2003), defined workplace spirituality, in their scientific inquiry on workplace spirituality, as:

'A framework of organizational values evidenced in the culture that promotes employees' experience of transcendence through the work process, facilitate their feeling of being connected in a way that provides feelings of compassion and joy.'

According to (Neal, 1997) workplace spirituality "can refer to the ways in which organizations structure themselves to support the spiritual growth of employees".

Studies have shown that people bring their whole selves to work. This is because they desire to be authentic in what they do and how they do it as they strive for meaning at work.

Organizations must therefore care for the whole employee's spiritual, emotional and physical well-being (Cacioppo, 2000)

2.2. Positive Work Attitude

David Laton says positive work attitude involve employee's attitude towards self, others and work. He defines positive environment as likelihood of a person to respond in a positive or negative way to someone or something in one's environment and it can be inferred by his or her behavior. Behavior of a person will directly impact on how employee feel towards the job; whether he like it or dislike it.

(Laton, 2006) Building a positive attitude begins with having confidence

Pawar (2009) divides workplace spirituality in three important dimensions which are Job satisfaction, Job involvement and Organizational Commitments.

2.3. Job Satisfaction

Dr.R.Anitha (2011) relates job satisfaction to the inner feelings of workers. She defines job satisfaction as a common attitude towards one's job, the divergence between the amount of reward workers received by the worker and the amount they believe they should receive.

According to Locke (1967) a classical definition of job satisfaction that define it comprehensively is "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience" he sees job satisfaction as appraisal a person makes about his own job.

Jacob Eskildsen, Kai Kristensen and Henrik Gjesing Antvor (2010) reviewed some previous studies and found five basic groups of constructs that result job satisfaction or dissatisfaction i.e. Organizational image, Organizational vision, Superiors, Co-workers, Conditions of work.

Hackman & Odham, (1975) Job satisfaction refers to the degree to which employees are satisfied and happy with their job.

Carsten C. Schermuly (2011) proved in his study on teachers that job satisfaction is very linked to emotional exhaustion. Thus, a decline in job satisfaction could lead to emotional exhaustion.

2.4. Job Involvement:

Involvement means "to pre occupy or absorb fully" a person who is involved in his job is one who takes it seriously, for whom important values are at stake in the job, whose moods and feelings are slightly affected by his job experience and who is mentally preoccupied with his job (Locke 1967).

Job Involvement has been considered as a cognitive credence state of psychological recognition with one's job (Kanungo, 1982; Lawler & Hall, 1970; Lodahl & Kejner, 1965; Rabinowitz & Hall, 1977). Lodahl and Kejner also define job involvement in expressions of contingency, self-esteem and performance, but this conceptual characterization is

not reflected in the most frequently used measuring procedures of job involvement (Kanungo, 1982; Rabinowitz & Hall, 1977).

Predecessor influences on job involvement contain job characteristics such as sovereignty, skill variety, significance and task identity (Hackman & Oldham, 1980), administrative behaviors such as consideration (Lance, 1991) and involvement (Smith & Brannick, 1990), and individual difference such as inside motivation (Gardner, Dunham, Cummings, & Pierce, 1989) and protestant work ethic (Brockner, Grover, & Blonder, 1988).

2.5. Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment can be stated as an employee attachment and loyalty with his organization and work as well (RT Mowday, LW Porter, RM Steers, 1982).

Organizational commitment can be said as an employee linkage with his organization (KA Arnold, 2001).

An employee attachment as a whole with his organization is called organizational commitment. It is widely different from other forms of commitment

3. Conceptual Framework

The literature review has been used as foundation in this research and the conceptual framework is built to describe the phenomena and some of its linked variables are considered for their relations. The model of this study is shown as:

for example work ethics endorsement, commitment with one's career, job engagement and other such commitments. (Lambert, D. Baker., et al, 2006)

Organizational commitment is an emotional and psychological attachment with an organization and convinces to retain in an organization. In this way employees will less likely to quit from the job and want to retain with his work and in organization (Meyer, Allen; 1996)

Employee's attachment, identification, involvement in an organization in which he is working and performing his work is called as organizational commitment (Allen and Meyer, 1991).

An employee involve in an organization and with his work with a strong belief toward acceptance of organization's goals, values and willingness to exert his knowledge, skills and abilities in behalf of his organization (R.T. Mowday, R.M. Steers & L.W. Porter; 1979).

Commitment is also act as a bond to an organization as a whole. Organization's goals and values alignment, behavioral investments in organization and motivation to stay in an organization are all contributed to an organizational commitment (R.T. Mowday, R.M. Steers & L.W. Porter; 1982).

Independent Variable

- Workplace Spirituality

Dependent Variable

- Job Satisfaction
- Job Involvement
- Organizational Commitment

4. Methodology

4.1. Population and Sampling Design

The population of this study consisted of employees (Lecturer and professors) working in different universities of province Punjab of Pakistan. Punjab was then further divided into clusters. These clusters were made on the basis of geographical locations of different divisions of Punjab. These divisions included Gujranwala, Lahore, Faisalabad, Sargodha, Jehlum, and Gujrat etc. through simple random sampling technique cluster of Gujranwala division was selected. These clusters based on divisional distribution were further divided into different strata which were based on District Level. Gujranwala division was subdivided into Sialkot, Gujrat, Gujranwala, and Mandi Baha-Ud-din Districts. From these districts Gujrat District through stratified random sampling was selected. After selecting Gujrat District universities and their campuses located in Gujrat were assembled. Among these campuses, Hafiz Hayat Campus was selected for being most populated area.

From University of Gujrat, employees (Lecturer and professors) to be studied were selected through random sampling. Hafiz Hayat Campus was thought to be very helpful target population. 140 questionnaires were completed while 39 were incomplete so appropriate responses shown were 101 (56%).

4.2. Data collection methods

A survey method was used for data collection. For this purpose a questionnaire had to be formulated. Questionnaire was formulated according to the items of base paper and some other former studies. Required changes were made in questionnaire by focusing the effect of workplace spirituality on Job Satisfaction, job involvement and organizational commitment after a quick review. Four variables had been used in the questionnaire which further has different items i.e. workplace spirituality consisted of 16 items, Job Satisfaction consisted of 12 items, and organizational commitment had 5 items. Workplace spirituality dimensions and items were developed by Dr. Harold Andrew Patrick and Amit Kumar, 2001 which we adopted from our base paper (Dr. Harold Andrew Patrick, 2011) and picked supervisory support items for management/ employee development dimensions from a study of Jaffrey H. Greenhaus, 1990. (Jaffrey H. Greehaus, 1990). Items of job satisfaction were also adopted from Jaffrey H. Greenhaus, 1990. (Jaffrey H. Greehaus, 1990). To measure employee involvement only relevant items were adopted and modified from Elsa M. Lopez's 26 items for measuring job performance. (Lopez, 1982)

A five point Likert scale (1- Strongly Disagree to 5-Strongly Agree) was used for the measurement of the given variables. For pre-testing purpose 25 questionnaires from actual sample were used and changes were made on the basis of responses.

4.3. Statistical tools

When data was collected, then it was analyzed in SPSS software. To check the reliability of our questionnaire, a Cronbach's Alpha was used. To check the relationships between workplace spirituality, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job involvement, a correlation was performed and to measure the degree of change, a regression analysis was performed. These all statistical tools were used to make our study more effective and accurate.

5. Data Analysis

5.1. Descriptive statistics

This analysis was done to analyze the demographic variables.

Data and descriptive statistics		
Age	Below 20	4 (4 Percent)
	21-30	35 (34.7Percent)
	31-40	28 (27.7 Percent)
	41-50	18 (17.8 Percent)
	Above 50	16 (15.8 Percent)
Gender	Male	54 (53.5 Percent)
	Female	47 (46.5 Percent)
Marital Status	Unmarried	44 (43.6 Percent)
	Married	57 (56.4 Percent)
Education Level	Bachelor	4 (4 Percent)
	Master	18 (17.8 Percent)
	MS/M.Phill	46 (45.5 Percent)
	PhD	33 (32.7 Percent)
Salary	5,001-15,000	1 (1.0 Percent)
	15,001-25,000	11(10.9 Percent)
	25,001-40,000	32 (31.7 Percent)
	40,001-55,000	33 (32.7 Percent)
	Above 55,000	24 (23.8 Percent)

The above descriptive table shows that there were total 101 respondents in which 4 were below 20 age (4 percent), 35 were between the age of 21-30 (34.7 percent), 28 were between the age of 31-40 age (27.7 percent), between 41-50 age were 18 (17.8 percent) and only 16 (15.8 percent) were above 50. From Gender statistics, male respondents were 54 (53.5 percent) and female were 47 (46.5 percent). Unmarried were 44 (43.6 percent) and married rate was 57 (56.4 percent). 4 (4 percent) had Bachelor degree, 18 (17.8 percent) had Master degree, 46 (45.5 percent) had MS/M.Phil degree and 33 (32.7 percent) had done PhD. Salary was also analyzed, there was only 1(1 percent) person who were getting 5,001-15,000, 11 (10.9 percent) were getting 15,001-25,000, 32 (31.7 percent) were between 20,001-40,000 salary range, 33 (32.7 percent) was getting between 40,001-55,000 and 24 (23.8 percent) were getting above 55,000.

5.2. Reliability test

Reliability of a questionnaire is very important for getting accurate results. In this study, a Cronbach's Alpha was used to check our questionnaire reliability and ensure about valid results. Reliability was checked individually as well as collectively of variables for our proposed model.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.955	50

The above reliability statistics shows the Cronbach's Alpha at 0.944 which is most significant value of our questionnaire. So, this is reliable questionnaire.

Reliability Test Cronbach's Alpha		
Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items
Workplace Spirituality	0.877	16
Job Satisfaction	0.803	11
Organizational Commitment	0.874	12
Job Involvement	0.843	11

The above table shows individual Cronbach's Alpha for each variable. All shows the reliability as these values are significant.

5.3. Correlation

After analysis of our data and interpretations, it is stated that there is a correlation between these proposed variables. Table of correlations is attached in appendix which describe that all of the variables have significant relationship. Correlations analysis shows the relationship between WS and JS at 0.768 which describe that there is positive relationship between workplace spirituality and job satisfaction. WS and OC relationship value is 0.709 which is a significant value and describe the positive relation between workplace spirituality and organizational commitment. WS and JI correlation shows 0.786 values which is also a significant value that has a positive relationship between workplace spirituality and job involvement.

5.4. Regression Results

The below table shows interpretations of our research are as under:

Hypothesis	IV	DV	Significance	R square	α	β
H1	WS	JS	0.000	0.590	9.874	0.768
H2	WS	OC	0.000	0.502	13.433	0.709
H3	WS	JI	0.000	0.618	8.808	0.786

IV= Independent variable, DV=Dependant variable, R square= Percent change

Equation for H1:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta x$$
$$Y (JS) = 9.874 + 0.768(WS)$$

Equation for H2:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta x$$
$$Y (OC) = 13.433 + 0.709 (WS)$$

Equation for H3:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta x$$
$$Y (JI) = 8.808 + 0.786 (WS)$$

WS and JS have significant relationship and R2 shows 0.590 which means that workplace spirituality impact on JS at rate of 59%. Workplace spirituality put 59% change on job satisfaction. WS and OC R2 value is 0.502 which means that career workplace spirituality put 50 % change in organizational commitment. WS with JI R2 value is 0.618 which shows that workplace spirituality put 61 % change on job involvement; this value shows that workplace spirituality has some relationship with job involvement.

6. Conclusion

The basic purpose behind conducting this study was to explore and determine the relationship between workplace spirituality, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job involvement. Literature review showed the significant relationship between workplace spirituality and job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job involvement. 101 respondents participated in our study and results concluded that workplace spirituality has a positive significant relationship with job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job involvement.

7. Limitations

The current research has several limitations which can provide an opportunity for further study in future. As we had not sufficient time to study and there was some lack of awareness about workplace spirituality among employees. Some respondents' biasness occurred to respond questionnaire. All workplace spirituality perspectives are not investigated. The target population was selected due to geographical benefit for data collection is another limitation to our study. No proper responses from respondents were also a major issue. Future researchers could attempt to overcome this through targeting larger firms where workplace spirituality practices are wider and could easily be seen and analyzed and are implemented properly. Employee psychological and other work life balance factors would be used in future researches.

8. Recommendations

However, this study can be further used for future research. This will help them out to determine the impacts of workplace spirituality to some other personal factors that might influence on this practice. Workplace spirituality will guide the supervisors and employees about importance of workplace spirituality and its impact on their job role and job performance. This study will also motivate the employees to improve and promote workplace spirituality. This will also aid in understanding the concept of workplace spirituality by organizations to promote and practice throughout the organization.

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Appendix

Questionnaire

SECTION-A

Profile of the Respondent:

Job Title: _____

Age:

- | | | |
|-----------------------------------|-----------------------------------|--------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Below 20 | <input type="checkbox"/> 21-30 | <input type="checkbox"/> 31-40 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 41-50 | <input type="checkbox"/> Above 50 | |

Gender:

- | | |
|-------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Male | <input type="checkbox"/> Female |
|-------------------------------|---------------------------------|

Marital Status:

- | | |
|------------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Unmarried | <input type="checkbox"/> Married |
|------------------------------------|----------------------------------|

Education Level:

- | | |
|------------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelors | <input type="checkbox"/> Masters |
| <input type="checkbox"/> MS/M.Phil | <input type="checkbox"/> PhD |

Salary:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 10,001- 25,000 | <input type="checkbox"/> 25,001-40,000 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 40,001- 55,000 | <input type="checkbox"/> Above 55,000 |

Jobs Changed: _____ (Number of organizations changed)

Job Experience: _____ (In years)

Please tick one of the following according to the details given below:

1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly Agree

1. WORKPLACE SPIRITUALITY						
1.	My spirit is energized by my work.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	My work is connected to what I think is important in life.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	I See a connection between my work and social good.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	I Understand what gives my work personal meaning.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	I Feel part of a community.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	I believe people support each other at my organization.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	I feel free to express my opinions.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	I think employees are linked with a common purpose.	1	2	3	4	5
9.	I believe employees genuinely care about each other.	1	2	3	4	5
10.	I feel positive about the values of the organization.	1	2	3	4	5
11.	My organization is concerned about the poor.	1	2	3	4	5
12.	I feel connected with the organization's goals.	1	2	3	4	5
13.	My organization cares about whether my spirit is energized.	1	2	3	4	5
14.	Organization cares about all its employees.	1	2	3	4	5
15.	Working cooperatively with others is valued.	1	2	3	4	5
16.	Organization is concerned about health of employees.	1	2	3	4	5
2. JOB SATISFACTION						
17.	I am satisfied with my job currently.	1	2	3	4	5
18.	My work environment is pleasant.	1	2	3	4	5
19.	I am extremely glad that I have chosen this company to work for, over other organizations.	1	2	3	4	5
20.	My fellow workers are supportive.	1	2	3	4	5
21.	My supervisors are co-operative.	1	2	3	4	5
22.	I am satisfied with my organization's policies.	1	2	3	4	5
23.	I am satisfied with my salary and wages.	1	2	3	4	5
24.	I have good advancement opportunities with my current organization.	1	2	3	4	5
25.	Organization's customers are good.	1	2	3	4	5
26.	My organization provides me complete support.	1	2	3	4	5
27.	In general, I don't like my job.(R)	1	2	3	4	5
3. ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT						
28.	I do not feel like "part of the family" at the organization.	1	2	3	4	5
29.	The organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	1	2	3	4	5
30.	I do not feel "emotionally attached" to the organization.	1	2	3	4	5
31.	I feel a strong sense of belonging to the organization.	1	2	3	4	5
32.	I am very likely to stay in this company for the next five years.	1	2	3	4	5
33.	For me, this company is the best of all possible organizations to work for.	1	2	3	4	5
34.	I will not give up this company easily.	1	2	3	4	5
35.	I seldom hear about or exposed to jobs outside my company that interest me.	1	2	3	4	5
36.	I really care about the fate of this organization.	1	2	3	4	5
37.	I am proud to tell others that I am a part of this organization.	1	2	3	4	5
38.	I feel that my values and my organization's values are similar.	1	2	3	4	5
39.	I talk about this organization to my friends as a great place to work.	1	2	3	4	5
4. JOB INVOLVEMENT						
40.	The most important things that happen to me involve my present job.	1	2	3	4	5
41.	To me, my job is only a small part of who I am.(R)	1	2	3	4	5
42.	I am very much involved personally in my job.	1	2	3	4	5
43.	Most of my interests are centered on my job.	1	2	3	4	5
44.	I have very strong ties with my present job that would be very difficult to break.	1	2	3	4	5
45.	Usually I feel detached from my job.(R)	1	2	3	4	5
46.	Most of my personal life goals are job-oriented.	1	2	3	4	5
47.	I consider my job to be very central to my existence	1	2	3	4	5
48.	I like to be absorbed in my job most of the time.	1	2	3	4	5
49.	I feel as if my organization's problems are my own.	1	2	3	4	5
50.	I would be happy to spend the rest of my career with my organization.	1	2	3	4	5

Frequency Table

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid male	54	53.5	53.5	53.5
female	47	46.5	46.5	100.0
Total	101	100.0	100.0	

Marital Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid unmarried	44	43.6	43.6	43.6
married	57	56.4	56.4	100.0
Total	101	100.0	100.0	

Education Level

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Bechelors	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
Masters	18	17.8	17.8	21.8
MS/ M.Phil	46	45.5	45.5	67.3
PhD	33	32.7	32.7	100.0
Total	101	100.0	100.0	

Salary

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 5,001-15,000	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
15,001-25000	11	10.9	10.9	11.9
25,001-40,000	32	31.7	31.7	43.6
40,001-55,000	33	32.7	32.7	76.2
Above 55,000	24	23.8	23.8	100.0
Total	101	100.0	100.0	

Correlations

		WS	JS	OC	JI
WS	Pearson Correlation	1	.768**	.709**	.786**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	101	101	101	101
JS	Pearson Correlation	.768**	1	.758**	.724**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	101	101	101	101
OC	Pearson Correlation	.709**	.758**	1	.683**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	101	101	101	101
JI	Pearson Correlation	.786**	.724**	.683**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	101	101	101	101

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.768 ^a	.590	.586	4.98620

a. Predictors: (Constant), WS

ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3542.071	1	3542.071	142.468	.000 ^a
Residual	2461.354	99	24.862		
Total	6003.426	100			

a. Predictors: (Constant), WS

b. Dependent Variable: JS

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.874	2.557		3.862	.000
	WS	.532	.045	.768	11.936	.000

a. Dependent Variable: JS

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.709 ^a	.502	.497	6.27085

a. Predictors: (Constant), WS

ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3925.717	1	3925.717	99.831	.000 ^a
Residual	3893.036	99	39.324		
Total	7818.752	100			

a. Predictors: (Constant), WS

b. Dependent Variable: OC

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.433	3.216		4.177	.000
	WS	.560	.056	.709	9.992	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OC

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.786 ^a	.618	.615	4.92106

a. Predictors: (Constant), WS

ANOVA^b

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3886.672	1	3886.672	160.495	.000 ^a
Residual	2397.466	99	24.217		
Total	6284.139	100			

a. Predictors: (Constant), WS

b. Dependent Variable: JI

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	8.808	2.523		3.490	.001
WS	.557	.044	.786	12.669	.000

a. Dependent Variable: JI